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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY – AN INVESTMENT FOR A SOUL

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Abstract

Objective- Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is basically a concept whereby companies decide voluntarily to contribute to a better society and a cleaner environment. It is represented by the contributions undertaken by companies to the society through its business activities and its social investment. The objective of this research paper is to study the regulatory framework of CSR activities in India applicable on corporates with reference to the Companies Act, 2013 as well as an analysis on the tax implications under the Income Tax Act, 1961. The secondary objective of the research is to study the benefits of CSR activities to the corporates.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- Secondary sources of data collection have been adopted for the study. The relevant and required data are collected from the national and international articles, MCA website, RBI Guidelines, Companies Act 2013, Income Tax Act, 1961, ICSI articles as well as website of Mahindra and Mahindra Limited.

Findings- This research is a deliberate attempt to conclude that CSR is just not a penny out of the pocket but a churning machine to accumulate dollars in the bank account.

Limitations- Present research is conceptualized and based on secondary data only.

Practical implications- The corporates could achieve right balance between company's profits and its social responsibility and hereby developing a healthy society in true social and economic sense.

Originality/Value- The paper includes practical examples of organizations following CSR activities and also includes literature review of CSR articles.

Keywords- Corporates, Corporate social responsibility, Companies Act 2013, Income Tax Act 1961.

INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is basically a concept whereby companies decide voluntarily to contribute to a better society and a cleaner environment. It is represented by the contributions undertaken by companies to the society through its business activities and its social investment. This is also to connect the concept of sustainable development to the company's level. The term CSR is imprecise and its application differs. The regulatory framework in India has though made certain clarifications for the CSR activities.

CSR is also called Corporate Citizenship or Corporate Responsibility. Generally, CSR is understood to be the way firms integrate social, environmental and economic concerns into their values, culture, decision making, strategy and operations in a transparent and accountable manner and thereby establish better practices within the firm, create wealth and improve society.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to R.K.Mittal, Neena Sinha and Archana Singh (2008), there is little evidence that companies with a code of ethics would generate significantly more economic value added (EVA) and market added value (MVA) than those without codes.

“Does Corporate Social Responsibility Influence Firm Performance of Indian Companies?” by Supriti Mishra and Damodar Suar (September 2010) findings indicate that stock-listed firms show responsible business practices and better financial performance than the non-stock-listed firms.

Peter Gampel, the Director of Business Valuation at the accounting firm Fiske & Company in Florida, in the United States, noted that a company's value is based on its tangible assets – such as its cash holdings, property and buildings – as well as its intangible assets. He also states that social responsibility does clearly have an impact on a company's value and profitability.

Companies that are socially responsible make their brands more attractive to consumers and are more appealing to high quality potential employees.

As per Deborah Doane Fall (2005) the market doesn't work as per the saying that by doing well it would be better. He proclaimed that it is the myth that CSR activities help the organizations in short term financial benefits and long term social benefits.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Secondary sources of data collection have been adopted for the study. The relevant and required data are collected from the national and international articles, MCA website, RBI Guidelines, Companies Act 2013, Income Tax Act, 1961, ICSI articles as well as website of Mahindra and Mahindra Limited.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the regulatory framework for CSR activities in India with reference to the Companies Act, 2013 and the tax implications under the Income Tax Act, 1961.
- To study the benefits of CSR activities to the corporates.

METHODOLOGY

The paper analysis the tax implications on corporates with reference to Income Tax Act, 1961 with governing provisions of Companies Act, 2013 u/s 135. An attempt is made to explain the benefits derived by corporates if good CSR activities are adopted with the help of secondary data.

With a view of studying the first objective the researcher explains the regulatory framework for CSR activities in India with reference to the Companies Act, 2013 and the tax implications under Income Tax Act, 1961.

Companies Act 2013: With the enactment of the Companies Act, 2013, India has become the forerunner to mandate spend on CSR activities through a statutory provision. While many

corporate houses have been traditionally engaged in doing CSR activities voluntarily, the new CSR provisions put formal and greater responsibility on companies in India to set out clear framework and processes to ensure strict compliance. However, what the Companies Act does is bring more companies into the fold and increase the total CSR spend.

- 1) **Applicability:** Section 135 of the Companies Act provides the threshold limit for applicability of the CSR to a Company i.e. (i) net worth of the company to be Rs500 crore or more; (ii) turnover of the company to be Rs1000 crore or more; (iii) net profit of the company to be Rs 5 crore or more. Further as per the CSR Rules, the provisions of CSR are not only applicable to Indian companies, but also applicable to branch and project offices of a foreign company in India.

- 2) **CSR Committee and Policy:** Every qualifying company requires spending of at least 2% of its average net profit for the immediately preceding 3 financial years on CSR activities. Further, the qualifying company will be required to constitute a CSR Committee of the Board of Directors consisting of 3 or more directors. For a qualifying private company at least two directors need to be appointed for CSR Committee. One of the directors so appointed in the CSR committee should be an independent director. The Committee shall formulate and recommend to the Board, a policy which shall indicate the activities to be undertaken (CSR Policy); recommend the amount of expenditure to be incurred on the activities referred and monitor the CSR Policy of the company. The Board shall take into account the recommendations made by the Committee and approve the CSR Policy of the company.

- 3) **Definition of the term CSR:** The term CSR has been defined under the CSR Rules which includes but is not limited to:
 - Projects or programs relating to activities specified in the Schedule; or
 - Projects or programs relating to activities undertaken by the Board in pursuance of recommendations of the CSR Committee as per the declared CSR policy subject to the condition that such policy covers subjects enumerated in the Schedule.

This definition of CSR assumes significance as it allows companies to engage in projects or programs relating to activities enlisted under the Schedule. Flexibility is also permitted to the companies by allowing them to choose their preferred CSR engagements that are in conformity with the CSR policy.

- 4) **Activities under CSR:** The activities that can be done by the company to achieve its CSR obligations include eradicating extreme hunger and poverty, promotion of education, promoting gender equality and empowering women, reducing child mortality and improving maternal health, combating human immunodeficiency virus, acquired, immune deficiency syndrome, malaria and other diseases, ensuring environmental sustainability, employment enhancing vocational skills, social business projects, contribution to the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund or any other fund set up by the Central Government or the State Governments for socio-economic development and relief and funds for the welfare of the Scheduled Castes, the Scheduled Tribes, other backward classes, minorities and women and such other matters as may be prescribed.
- 5) **CSR Expenditure:** CSR expenditure shall include all the expenditure including contributions to corpus the projects or programs relating to CSR activities approved by the Board on the recommendation of its CSR committee, but does not include any expenditure on an item not in conformity or not in line with activities which fall within the purview of Schedule VII of the Act.
- 6) **Display of CSR activities on its website:** The Board of Directors of the company shall, after taking into account the recommendation of CSR committee, approve the CSR policy for the company and disclose the contents of such policy in its report and the same shall be displayed on the company's website, if any, as per the particulars specified in the Annexure.
- 7) **Local Area:** Under the Companies Act, preference should be given to local areas and the areas where the company operates. Company may also choose to associate with 2 or

more companies for fulfilling the CSR activities provided that they are able to report individually.

The company can also make the annual report of CSR activities in which they mention the average net profit for the 3 financial years and also prescribed CSR expenditure but if the company is unable to spend the minimum required expenditure the company has to give the reasons in the Board Report for non-compliance so that there are no penal provisions attracted by it.

Overview of tax implications of CSR expenditures as per the provisions of Income Tax Act, 1961

The Finance Act, 2014 has brought a very radical and far reaching amendment as far as CSR expenditures are concerned. There was a lot of expectation that as a corollary to the CSR related amendment in the companies act there will be a corresponding amendment in the Income Tax Act, 1961 allowing CSR expenditure as deductions under section 37. On the contrary the Finance Act has proposed that the CSR expenditure shall not be allowed as expenditure under section 37 of the Income Tax Act 1961. However any CSR expenditure which is allowed as deduction under other sections such as section 30, 32, 35, 35AC, 80G etc. is permissible.

Now the tax treatment will be different for various types of permissible CSR activities. If the company directly undertakes CSR expenditure there will be no tax benefit, therefore, to spend 2% of the CSR the company may lose the tax benefit it's available otherwise.

If the corporate undertakes CSR expenditures through 80G registered NGO's (including its own foundation) then to spend 2% of CSR the company shall have some tax benefit as such contributions provide 50% tax benefits. Further if a company undertakes a CSR activities through institutions registered under section 35CCA, 35AC, 35CCC, 35CCD of the Income Tax Act 1961 or through funds like the Prime Minister Relief Fund, National Defence Fund having 100% tax benefit under section 80G. Hence, corporates would be more inclined to fund through such mode.

Further if the corporate undertakes CSR activities through institutions registered u/s 35 for scientific research or social research then it may get 125% -175% tax advantages, but the choice of activities will be reduced and the funds will go towards research and not to the direct field programmes.

With a view of studying the second objective the researcher explains the benefits of CSR activities to the corporates

Business cannot exist in isolation; business cannot be oblivious to social development. The CSR of business can be integrated into the business purpose so as to build a positive synergy between the two.

Enhanced brand image and reputation: CSR creates a favourable brand image, which attracts customers to organizations that perform well with regard to CSR and build reputation, while those that perform poorly. Brand equity, is founded on valued such as trust, credibility, reliability, quality and consistency.

Increased sales and customer loyalty: It has been observed that a strong record of CSR has improved customer commitment and satisfaction and bonding with the organization. If the customer likes the company, he or she will buy more products or services and will be less willing to change to another brand. Also they would be ready to shell out a premium amount to buy the products.

- Corporate social responsibility is an intangible asset that in some cases is integrally linked to a company's profits – such as **Starbuck's**, which markets its coffee as beneficial to the growers who produce it. In the fact that its prices are higher than a generic cup of coffee at the convenience store. Yet the customers are willing to pay those higher prices for a cup of coffee.
- **IBM study** “Attaining Sustainable Growth through corporate social responsibility”. The majority of business executives believe that CSR activities are giving the firms competitive advantage, primarily due to favourable responses from the consumers.

- **Better Business Journey**, UK Small Business Consortium: “88% of consumers said they were more likely to buy from a company that supports and engages in activities to improve society.”

Satisfied employees: CSR builds up a positive image encouraging social involvement of employees, which in return develops a sense of loyalty towards the organization, helping in creating a dedicated workforce proud of its company. This ensures employees retention in the organization.

- Mahindra and Mahindra Limited CSR activity **NANHI KALI** which provides educational support (material and academic) to underprivileged girls. In the Financial Year 2014-15 the project supported the education of 1, 13,124 girls. The project enabled the employees to adopt a girl and bear her educational expenses. By doing so now the employees too feel that they have done some good to the society. The amount spent by the employees towards the donation to this fund is later accounted as a tax benefit under section 80G of the Income Tax Act, 1961.

Positive public relations: CSR provides the opportunity to share positive stories online. Companies no longer have to waste money on expensive advertising campaigns. Instead they can generate free publicity and get benefit by word of mouth.

Reduced regulatory oversight: Companies that demonstrate that they are engaging in practices that satisfy and go beyond regulatory compliance requirements are being given less scrutiny by both national and the local government entities. In many cases, such companies are subject to fewer inspections and paperwork and may be given preference or “fast track” treatment when applying for operating permits, zoning variances or other forms of governmental permission.

Costs reductions: Yes, you read this correctly. A CSR program doesn't have to cost money. On the contrary, if conducted properly a company can reduce costs through CSR activities by practicing the following measures:

- Efficient staff hire retention
- Implementing energy savings programs
- Managing potential risks and liabilities more effectively

- Less investment in traditional advertising

Long term benefits: CSR is for the short term and also about achieving long term results with business continuity. Large businesses refer to shaping a more sustainable society.

- Vodafone 2010 report- “Deliver a sustainable society in which business and its stakeholders can prosper in the long term.”

CONCLUSION

The introduction of section 135 in the Companies Act is a welcome step which will boost much required social projects with some professional management of the private sector. Money spent on all CSR works cannot be counted as business expenditure but certain social welfare spending activities could be considered for tax benefits.

CSR has inherent value for a company. The exact dollar figure on that value may never be clearly quantified but the general trend towards greater corporate engagement in social issues is one that will have long-term impacts on the community development. The impact of CSR could be observed with motivated employees, loyal customers, brand image in the market, credibility of the corporates in financial institutions, enhanced goodwill reflecting in the balance sheet of corporates and many more.

Thereby the very traditional myth regarding CSR activities has been slashed by the corporates. Earlier it was considered that CSR activities have no impact on the short term financial returns and long term social benefits to the organization. But it could be observed from this research that sales can eventually increase due to customer loyalty and also by building the brand image which can have long term impact on the corporates.

The purpose of this research is to achieve right balance between company's profits and its social responsibility and hereby developing a healthy society in true social and economic sense.

Thereby, a half- filled glass of water would be an ideal approach to look at the CSR activities conducted by organizations. In reality the optimistic approach towards CSR would not only pave the way towards rendering services to society but also a step forward in attaining sustainable development.

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